

Modified Deficiencies of q-Difference Equations of Zero Order

Shilpa N.¹ and Achala L. Nargund²

^{1,2}P. G. Department of Mathematics, M. E. S. College, Bangalore-560 003, INDIA.

Abstract: In this paper, we deal with the modified deficiencies of q-difference equations and give some improvements for special types of meromorphic functions that would throw more light on the relative defects of difference polynomials, which extends the results of Toda [9], Sarangi and Patil [8], Bhoosnurmath S. S and Shankar. M. Patil [2].

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1. Introduction, Results and Definitions

For $a \in \mathbb{C}$, Milloux [7] introduced the concept of absolute defect of α with respect to the derivative f' . This definition was further extended by Hiong [5]. He introduced

$$\delta_r(\alpha, f^{(k)}) = 1 - \limsup_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{N\left(t, \frac{1}{f^{(k)} - \alpha}\right)}{T(t, f)}$$

is called as the "Relative defect of the value α with respect to $f^{(k)}$ ", the suffix "r" in the left hand side of above is just to denote the "relative" defect in contrast to the usual defect

$$\delta(a, f) = 1 - \limsup_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{N\left(t, \frac{1}{f - \alpha}\right)}{T(t, f)}$$

and the "absolute" defect

$$\delta_a(a, f) = 1 - \limsup_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{N\left(t, \frac{1}{f - \alpha}\right)}{T(t, f)}$$

and found several other relations between the relative defect and the usual defect. We define similar difference analogue of relative defect and absolute defect with respect to difference polynomial $P(f)$ as follows.

$$\delta_r^q(\alpha, P(f)) = 1 - \limsup_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{N_q\left(t, \frac{1}{P(f) - \alpha}\right)}{T(t, f)}$$

is called "q" difference absolute defect of α with respect to $P(f)$ and

$$\delta_a^q(\alpha, P(f)) = 1 - \limsup_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{N_q\left(t, \frac{1}{P(f) - \alpha}\right)}{T(t, P(f))}$$

is called "q" difference absolute defect with respect to $P(f)$.

Also as a natural q-difference analogue of $\bar{N}(r, a)$ is $\tilde{N}_q(r, a) = N(r, a) - N_q(r, a)$

as a result we have an analogue of $\Theta(a, f)$ as

$$\Pi_q(a, f) = 1 - \limsup_{r \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\tilde{N}_q(r, a)}{T(r, f)}.$$

All notations and terminology of the work follows from Hayman [4](1964). By $S(t, f)$ we mean quantity satisfying $S(t, f) = o[T(r, f)]$ as $r \rightarrow \infty$ possibly outside a set r of finite linear measure.

Definition 1. [2]: A monomial in f is an expression of the form

$$M_j(f) = f^{n_{0j}} f(q_1 z)^{n_{1j}} f(q_2 z)^{n_{2j}} \dots f(q_k z)^{n_{kj}},$$

where $n_{0j}, n_{1j}, n_{2j}, \dots, n_{kj}$ are non-negative integers. $\gamma_{M_j} = n_{0j} + n_{1j} + n_{2j} + \dots + n_{kj}$ is called the degree of

the monomial and $\Gamma_{M_j} = n_{0j} + 2n_{1j} + 3n_{2j} + \dots + (k+1)n_{kj} = \sum_{i=0}^k (i+1)n_{ij}$ the weight of $M_j(f)$.

$P_q(f) = \sum_{j=1}^q a_j M_j[f(qz)]$, where $a_i (i=1, 2, \dots, n)$ are constants, then $P(f)$ is called a differential polynomials in f of degree γ_{P_q} and the weight Γ_{P_q} , $P_q(f)$ are defined as follows, $\gamma_{P_q} = \max_{1 \leq j \leq q} \gamma_{M_j}$ and $\Gamma_{P_q} = \max_{1 \leq j \leq q} \Gamma_{M_j}$, also we call the number $\underline{\gamma}_{P_q} = \min_{1 \leq j \leq q} \gamma_{M_j}$ the lower degree of $P(f)$.

If $\overline{\gamma}_{P_q} = \underline{\gamma}_{P_q} = \gamma_{P_q}$, $P_q(f)$ is called a Homogeneous polynomial in f , otherwise Non-homogeneous.

Definition 2.[1]: let $q \in C - \{0, 1\}$ and $a \in C$. We define the counting function $n_q(r, a)$ to be the number of points z_0 in the disk of radius r centered at the origin such that $f(z_0) = a$, where the contribution to $n_q(r, a)$ is the number of equal terms in the beginning of Taylor series expansion of $f(z)$ and $f(qz)$ in a neighbourhood of z_0 . We call such points q-separated a-points of f in the disc $\{z : |z| \leq r\}$. The number of q-separated pole pairs $n_q(r, \infty)$ is the number of q-separated 0-pairs of $1/f$. This means that if f has a pole with multiplicity p at z_0 and another pole with multiplicity s at qz_0 then this pair is counted $\min\{p, s\} + m$ times in $n_q(r, \infty)$, where m is the number of equal terms in the beginning of Laurent series expansion of $f(z)$ and $f(qz)$ in a neighbourhood of z_0 .

Toda [9](1970) proved the following result.

Theorem A. If $f(z)$ is a transcendental meromorphic function in $|z| < \infty$, then

$$\sum_{a \neq \infty} \delta_a(\alpha) \leq \liminf_{r \rightarrow \infty} \frac{T_\alpha(r, f')}{T_\alpha(r, f)} \leq \limsup_{r \rightarrow \infty} \frac{T_\alpha(r, f')}{T_\alpha(r, f)} \leq 2 - \Theta_\alpha(\infty, f).$$

Later, Sarangi and Patil [8] proved the following results.

Theorem B. If $f(z)$ is a transcendental meromorphic function in $|z| < \infty$, then for any positive integer I ,

$$\sum_{a \neq \infty} \delta_\alpha(a) \leq \liminf_{r \rightarrow \infty} \frac{T_\alpha(r, f^{(I)})}{T_\alpha(r, f)} \leq \limsup_{r \rightarrow \infty} \frac{T_\alpha(r, f^{(I)})}{T_\alpha(r, f)} \leq (I+I) - I\Theta_\alpha(\infty, f).$$

Theorem C. If $f(z)$ is a transcendental meromorphic function in $|z| < \infty$, then for any positive integer I ,

$$\frac{1}{(I+I) - I\Theta_\alpha(\infty)} \sum_{a \neq \infty} \delta_\alpha(a) \leq \delta_\alpha(0, f^{(I)}).$$

Again Shankar. M. Pawar and Bhoosnurmath S. S [2](2002) extended the above results for homogeneous differential polynomials and proved the following results.

Theorem D. If $f(z)$ is a transcendental meromorphic function in $|z| < \infty$, then

$$\sum_{a \neq \infty} \delta_\alpha(a) \leq \liminf_{r \rightarrow \infty} \frac{T_\alpha(r, P(f))}{T_\alpha(r, f)} \leq \limsup_{r \rightarrow \infty} \frac{T_\alpha(r, P(f))}{T_\alpha(r, f)} \leq [\Gamma_P - (\Gamma_P - \gamma_P)\Theta_\alpha(\infty, f)]$$

where $P(f)$ is a homogeneous differential polynomial, not involving the f term.

Theorem E. Let $f(z)$ be a transcendental meromorphic function in the finite plane, $P(f)$ is a homogeneous differential polynomial, then

$$\frac{\gamma_P}{\Gamma_P - (\Gamma_P - \gamma_P)\Theta_\alpha(\infty, f)} \sum_{a \in \mathbb{C}} \delta_\alpha(a) \leq \delta_\alpha(0, P(f)).$$

We extend the above results to the difference polynomials and prove the following results.

Theorem 1.1. Let $f(z)$ be a transcendental meromorphic function of zero order with $P(f)$ as a homogeneous difference polynomial. For $f^n(0) \neq \infty, a \neq 0, \infty$ and for $P[f(0)] \neq 0$. We have

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma_{P_q} \sum_{a \in \mathbb{C}} \delta_\alpha(a_j) + 2 - [\Pi_q(\infty, f) + \delta_\alpha^q(\infty, f)] &\leq \liminf_{r \rightarrow \infty} \frac{T_\alpha(r, P_q(f))}{T_\alpha(r, f)} \\ &\leq \limsup_{r \rightarrow \infty} \frac{T_\alpha(r, P_q(f))}{T_\alpha(r, f)} \leq \Gamma_{P_q} - (\Gamma_{P_q} - \gamma_{P_q})\Theta_\alpha(\infty, f). \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 1.2. Let $f(z)$ be a transcendental meromorphic function of zero order in the finite plane with $P(f)$ as a homogeneous difference polynomial. For $f^n(0) \neq \infty, a \neq 0, \infty$ and for $P[f(0)] \neq 0$. We have

$$\frac{\gamma_{P_q}}{\Gamma_{P_q} - (\Gamma_{P_q} - \gamma_{P_q})\Theta_\alpha(\infty, f)} \sum_{a \in \mathbb{C}} \delta_\alpha(a) \leq \delta_\alpha^q(0, P(f)) + \Pi_q(\infty, P(f)) - 1.$$

2. Some Lemmas

To our main results we need the following Lemmas.

Lemma 2.1. ([2]). If $f(z)$ is a transcendental meromorphic function and $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_q$ are distinct elements, then

$$\gamma_P \sum_{j=1}^q m_\alpha(r, a_j, f) \leq T_\alpha(r, P(f)) - N(r, 0, P(f)) + S_\alpha(r, f)$$

or

$$\gamma_P \sum_{j=1}^q m_\alpha(r, a_j, f) \leq m_\alpha \left(r, \frac{1}{P(f)} \right) + S_\alpha(r, f)$$

where $P(f)$ is a homogeneous differential polynomial of degree γ_P .

Lemma 2.2. ([3]) If $Q[f]$ is a differential polynomial in f with arbitrary meromorphic coefficients q_j $1 \leq j \leq n$, then

$$m(r, Q[f]) \leq \gamma_Q m(r, f) + \sum_{j=1}^n m(r, a_j) + S(r, f).$$

Lemma 2.3. ([6]) If $f(z)$ is a transcendental meromorphic function then

$$N(r, P(f)) \leq \gamma_P N(r, f) + (\Gamma_P - \gamma_P) \bar{N}(r, f) + S(r, f).$$

3. Proofs of The Theorems.

In this section we present the proofs of the main results.

Proof of Theorem 1.1.

By Lemma 2.2 and Lema 2.3, we have

$$m_\alpha(r, P_q[f]) \leq \gamma_{P_q} m_\alpha(r, f) + S_\alpha(r, f)$$

and

$$N_\alpha(r, P_q[f]) \leq \gamma_{P_q} N_\alpha(r, f) + (\Gamma_{P_q} - \gamma_{P_q}) \bar{N}_\alpha(r, f) + S_\alpha(r, f).$$

Then we get,

$$T_\alpha(r, P_q[f]) \leq \gamma_{P_q} T_\alpha(r, f) + (\Gamma_{P_q} - \gamma_{P_q}) \bar{N}_\alpha(r, f) + S_\alpha(r, f).$$

Dividing by $T_\alpha(r, f)$ and taking limit superior both sides we get

$$\begin{aligned} \limsup_{r \rightarrow \infty} \frac{T_\alpha(r, P_q(f))}{T_\alpha(r, f)} &= \gamma_{P_q} + (\Gamma_{P_q} - \gamma_{P_q}) \limsup_{r \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\bar{N}_\alpha(r, f)}{T_\alpha(r, f)} \\ \limsup_{r \rightarrow \infty} \frac{T_\alpha(r, P_q(f))}{T_\alpha(r, f)} &\leq \gamma_{P_q} + (\Gamma_{P_q} - \gamma_{P_q}) [1 - \Theta_\alpha(\infty, f)] \\ &\leq \Gamma_{P_q} - (\Gamma_{P_q} - \gamma_{P_q}) \Theta_\alpha(\infty, f). \end{aligned} \quad (3.1)$$

On the other hand by Lemma 2.1, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma_{P_q} \sum_{j=1}^q m_\alpha(r, a_j, f) &\leq m_\alpha \left(r, \frac{1}{P_q(f)} \right) + S_\alpha(r, f) \\ &\leq T_\alpha \left(r, \frac{1}{P_q(f)} \right) - N_\alpha \left(r, \frac{1}{P_q(f)} \right) + S_\alpha(r, f) \end{aligned}$$

or

$$\begin{aligned}
T_\alpha\left(r, \frac{1}{P_q(f)}\right) &\geq \gamma_{P_q} \sum_{j=1}^q m_\alpha(r, a_j, f) + N_\alpha\left(r, \frac{1}{P_q(f)}\right) + S_\alpha(r, f) \\
&\geq \gamma_{P_q} \sum_{j=1}^q m_\alpha(r, a_j, f) + \tilde{N}_q\left(r, \frac{1}{P_q(f)}\right) + N_q\left(r, \frac{1}{P_q(f)}\right) + S_\alpha(r, f) \\
\limsup_{r \rightarrow \infty} \frac{T_\alpha(r, P_q(f))}{T_\alpha(r, f)} &\geq \gamma_{P_q} \sum_{j=1}^q \delta_\alpha(a_j) + [1 - \Pi_q(\infty, f)] + [1 - \delta_\alpha^q(\infty, f)] + S_\alpha(r, f) \\
&\geq \gamma_{P_q} \sum_{j=1}^q \delta_\alpha(a_j) + 2 - [\Pi_q(\infty, f) + \delta_\alpha^q(\infty, f)] + S_\alpha(r, f).
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned}
\gamma_{P_q} \sum_{a \in C} \delta_\alpha(a_j) + 2 - [\Pi_q(\infty, f) + \delta_\alpha^q(\infty, f)] &\leq \liminf_{r \rightarrow \infty} \frac{T_\alpha(r, P_q(f))}{T_\alpha(r, f)} \\
&\leq \limsup_{r \rightarrow \infty} \frac{T_\alpha(r, P_q(f))}{T_\alpha(r, f)} \leq \Gamma_{P_q} - (\Gamma_{P_q} - \gamma_{P_q}) \Theta_\alpha(\infty, f).
\end{aligned}$$

Corollary 1. If $f(z)$ is a transcendental meromorphic function with $\sum_{a \in C} \delta_\alpha(a) = 1$, $\Theta_\alpha(\infty) = 1$ and $\Pi_q(\infty, f) + \delta_\alpha^q(\infty, f) = 2$ then $T_\alpha(r, P_q(f)) \sim \gamma_{P_q} T_\alpha(r, f)$.

Corollary 2 If $f(z)$ is a transcendental meromorphic function in $|z| < \infty$, then if $\Gamma_{P_q} = 2$, $\gamma_{P_q} = 1$, $\sum_{a \in C} \delta_\alpha(a, f) = 2$ and $\Pi_q(\infty, f) + \delta_\alpha^q(\infty, f) = 2$ then

$$\lim_{r \rightarrow \infty} \frac{T_\alpha(r, P_q(f))}{T_\alpha(r, f)} \leq 2 - \Theta_\alpha(\infty, f).$$

Proof of Theorem 1.2. By Lemma 2.1

$$\begin{aligned}
\gamma_{P_q} \sum_{j=1}^q m_\alpha(r, a_j, f) &\leq m_\alpha\left(r, \frac{1}{P_q(f)}\right) + S_\alpha(r, f) \\
&\leq T_\alpha\left(r, \frac{1}{P_q(f)}\right) - N_\alpha\left(r, \frac{1}{P_q(f)}\right) + S_\alpha(r, f) \\
&\leq T_\alpha(r, P_q(f)) - \tilde{N}_q\left(r, \frac{1}{P_q(f)}\right) - N_q\left(r, \frac{1}{P_q(f)}\right) + S_\alpha(r, f)
\end{aligned}$$

Dividing by $T_\alpha(r, f)$ and taking limsup on both sides, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
\gamma_{P_q} \sum_{i=1}^q \delta_\alpha(a_i, f) &\leq \limsup_{r \rightarrow \infty} \frac{T_\alpha(r, P_q(f))}{T_\alpha(r, f)} - \limsup_{r \rightarrow \infty} \left[\frac{\tilde{N}_q \left(r, \frac{1}{P_q(f)} \right) + N_q \left(r, \frac{1}{P_q(f)} \right)}{T_\alpha(r, P_q(f))} \right] \\
&\quad + \limsup_{r \rightarrow \infty} \frac{T_\alpha(r, P_q(f))}{T_\alpha(r, f)} + \limsup_{r \rightarrow \infty} \frac{S_\alpha(r, f)}{T_\alpha(r, f)} \\
&\leq \limsup_{r \rightarrow \infty} \left[1 - \frac{\tilde{N}_q \left(r, \frac{1}{P_q(f)} \right) + N_q \left(r, \frac{1}{P_q(f)} \right)}{T_\alpha(r, P_q(f))} \right] \cdot \limsup_{r \rightarrow \infty} \frac{T_\alpha(r, P_q(f))}{T_\alpha(r, f)} \\
&\quad + \limsup_{r \rightarrow \infty} \frac{S_\alpha(r, f)}{T_\alpha(r, f)} \\
&\leq [\delta^q(0, P(f)) + \Pi_q(\infty, P(f)) - 1] \limsup_{r \rightarrow \infty} \frac{T_\alpha(r, P_q(f))}{T_\alpha(r, f)} + o(1).
\end{aligned}$$

By Theorem 2.1, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
\gamma_{P_q} \sum_{i=1}^q \delta_\alpha(a_i, f) &\leq [\delta^q(0, P(f)) + \Pi_q(\infty, P(f)) - 1] \cdot \limsup_{r \rightarrow \infty} \frac{T_\alpha(r, P_q(f))}{T_\alpha(r, f)} \\
&\leq [\delta^q(0, P(f)) + \Pi_q(\infty, P(f)) - 1] \Gamma_{P_q} - (\Gamma_{P_q} - \gamma_{P_q}) \Theta_\alpha(\infty, f).
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$\frac{\gamma_{P_q}}{\Gamma_{P_q} - (\Gamma_{P_q} - \gamma_{P_q}) \Theta_\alpha(\infty, f)} \sum_{a \in C} \delta_\alpha(a) \leq \delta^q(0, P(f)) + \Pi_q(\infty, P(f)) - 1.$$

Corollary 3. If $f(z)$ is a meromorphic function with $\Theta_\alpha(\infty, f) = 1, \Pi_q(\infty, P(f)) = 1$ then

$$\sum_{a \in C} \delta_\alpha(a) \leq \delta^q(0, P(f)).$$

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